

Academic Integrity in Higher Education: Faculty Perceptions, Strategies, and Digital Challenges in the Digital Age

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ABSTRACT

The study surveyed faculty across various disciplines and experience levels using a mixed-method approach, showing significant insights into their perceptions, methods, and challenges towards Academic Integrity. The findings indicate a high awareness of academic dishonesty, with most university students reportedly engaging in such acts. Faculty employ diverse strategies to combat academic dishonesty, including syllabus integrity expectations, ethical dialogues, and varied assessment formats. However, challenges like the influence of the digital environment, online learning issues, and student pressure persist. The study highlights the need for institutional policies and faculty development programs emphasizing ethical conduct and practical engagement in academic integrity. Recommendations include enhancing syllabus communication, engaging in ethical dialogues, and using varied assessment formats and teaching learning method along with the modification in pedagogies. The study aligns with Aristotle's virtue ethics, advocating for the development of moral virtues through practical engagements. Key findings highlight the role of Ethical Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy in addressing Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven academic dishonesty, suggesting the importance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) monitoring tools and Ethical Education.

Keywords: Academic Integrity, Academic Dishonesty, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Challenges, Ethical Conduct, Teaching Learning Methods, Virtue Ethics

INTRODUCTION

Academic integrity is a commitment to honesty, trust, fairness, equity, respect, and responsibility, as well as translating these values into action (Bretag & Mahmud, 2016). While research into academic integrity, COVID-19, and increased online education brought serious discussions and almost a moral panic about academic integrity, technology cheating is more accessible for students, and ideas that students are 'getting away' with large-scale cheating in the higher education system. (Curtis & Tremayne, 2021) According to research by Dr. Donald McCabe, a founder of ICAI (International Centre for Academic Integrity), studies on cheating in colleges and universities began in 1990 and have been ongoing under ICAI's leadership. McCabe's initial research and subsequent follow-up studies reveal that over 60% of university students openly admit to engaging in academic dishonesty (ICAI). In March 2020, ICAI researchers surveyed using an updated version of McCabe's study 840 students from 5 institutions, including a private university, two large public universities, a small public university, and a small private liberal arts college. The study found significant rates of key cheating behaviors among the participants (ICAI). (McCabe, 2001)

In today's world, dishonesty is an alarming issue permeating various spheres of life, from media and politics to business and education. Academic dishonesty is a severe offense that has repercussions not just for the individual involved but also for the educational institution and those in close association with the individual. Engaging in academic deceit can lead to a decline in one's professional capabilities, erosion of personal ethics, and the onset of mistrust. Ethics is defined as the discipline dealing with what is good, what is terrible, and what is a moral duty and obligation. (Mishra, 2017).

Research Objectives

- I. To gain insights into faculty member's views on the importance of academic honesty in teaching, learning, and assessments.
- II. To identify the strategies and approaches faculty employ to promote academic integrity among students.

- III. To investigate the challenges faculty face in fostering academic integrity and how they address them.
- IV. How do faculty members perceive the significance of academic honesty in the educational process, and how does it influence their teaching practices?

Research Questions

- I. What strategies and methods do faculty use to promote a culture of academic integrity among students?
- II. What challenges do faculty encounter when fostering academic integrity, and what strategies do they employ to overcome them?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Academic integrity embodies the principles and behaviors that guide the actions of academics in teaching, research, and service (Chen & Macfarlane, 2016). The Centre of Academic Integrity pinpoints honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility, and courage as its foundational values (ICAI, 2013). Students and Faculty must adhere to these values for an academic environment to thrive. Academic integrity ensures the credibility and trustworthiness of a university's attempts Global initiatives, like the OECD's Future of Education and Skills 2030 report (Hodge et al., 2021), highlight the importance of respect, fairness, personal and social responsibility, integrity, and self-awareness in building inclusive and sustainable societies. Academic leaders are recommended to embed these values as learning outcomes in university curricula and consider them in the selection criteria for faculty and staff. These values align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and 2030 agenda. (Mishra et al., 2024) Elucidate on Social impact assessment (SIA) which highlights essential factors such as expanding access, personalizing learning, and preparing students for the digital age this have both positive and negative sides.

Studies suggest that to reduce academic dishonesty effectively, it is vital to comprehend the elements that affect the two main groups involved in this issue: students who take part in such dishonest activities and faculty members who bear the duty of identifying and preventing these behaviors (Albers-Miller et al., 2000). Academic dishonesty interrupts the collaborative spirit of higher education, where students, faculty, and administrators work together to support students in achieving their goals (Whitley Jr & Keith-Spiegel, 2001). Academic integrity is crucial in education, especially for achieving excellence in learning. It serves a dual purpose in a university setting: firstly, to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for a chosen profession, and secondly, to develop an ethical mindset that guides sound decision-making in the workplace. (Guerrero-Dib et al., 2020)

The prevalence of academic dishonesty in educational institutions reflects a broader decline in ethical behavior in society, where self-centeredness often takes precedence over concern for others (Barratt, 2013). This unethical behavior extends beyond institutional boundaries, facilitated by advanced technological tools that allow access to information from distant sources (Stone et al., 2009).

Academic dishonesty takes various forms, including copying test responses, failing to cite sources properly, and purchasing research papers and passing them off as one's work (Daffin & Jones, 2018). The acceptance of academic dishonesty by faculty members not only influences student's perceptions of academic integrity but also affects their views on the acceptance of academic dishonesty at their institutions (Abusafia et al., 2018). With the emergence of online distance education institutions, verifying the identity of students to ensure the authenticity of their work has become a significant concern. This issue is not limited to digital distance institutions. It also affects traditional institutions, as students can outsource assignments or download materials from websites and submit them as work (Ellahi et al., 2013). Efforts to reduce academic misconduct have been challenging, and despite attempts to address it, the incidence of academic misconduct remains high (Srirejeki et al., 2022).

Academic misconduct is a growing concern across the tertiary education sector, affecting universities globally (Birks et al., 2020). Students resort to cheating for various reasons, including the desire to maintain good grades, fear of failure, viewing school or professors as biased, limited study time, observing peers cheat without consequences, parental pressure to excel, and the complexity of the course material. (McCabe, 2001).

Research Gaps

The literature review identifies critical research gaps in academic integrity. There is a need for detailed studies on the effectiveness of strategies to promote integrity in online learning, mainly due to the shift to virtual education from COVID-

19. Additionally, exploring how faculty attitudes toward academic dishonesty affect student behavior and policy adoption is crucial. Further research is also necessary to evaluate the impact of faculty training programs on academic integrity, guiding the development of effective faculty development initiatives. Addressing these gaps can substantially improve academic integrity in higher education.

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research offers valuable insights and practical recommendations to enhance academic integrity in education. It identifies practical approaches to promote honesty, informs support mechanisms, and shapes policies in educational institutions. Fostering integrity improves the learning environment, student engagement, and institutional reputation, benefiting the broader academic community.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study aligns with Aristotle's virtue ethics, emphasizing the development of virtues like honesty and fairness through practice, as outlined in his work, *Nicomachean Ethics*. The study applies Aristotle's theory by adopting interactive and practical learning methods, showing that virtues are best learned through active engagement. This approach operationalizes Aristotle's principles in modern education, emphasizing the cultivation of ethical behavior in academic settings; according to (Doukas et al., 2021), integrating virtue ethics into educational curricula is crucial for fostering ethical behavior among students, as it provides a framework for developing moral virtues through practical engagement and habituation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This pilot study systematically explores faculty perspectives on academic integrity, addressing the enduring issue of academic dishonesty. We employed purposive sampling across various Higher Education branches in Oman, resulting in a 64% response rate from 32 completed surveys out of 50 distributed. The survey instrument included closed and open-ended items, allowing for quantitative and qualitative data collection. Descriptive statistics and thematic analysis were used to examine perceptions of academic integrity among faculty. Contingency tables were employed to explore variable relationships. The study offers evidence-based strategies to enhance academic integrity, emphasizing the vital role of faculty. SPSS 29 was used for quantitative analysis. Participation in the survey was voluntary, with assurances of anonymity and confidentiality upheld to encourage candid responses.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Before the data analysis, the reliability of the survey responses was assessed. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was employed to evaluate the questionnaire's internal consistency, yielding a value of 0.824. This indicates a high level of internal consistency, suggesting that all items are suitable for inclusion.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for Survey Variables

Variable	N	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
Age	31	2.29	2.00	0.824
Education	31	2.35	2.00	0.551
Experience	31	4.03	4.00	1.224
Specialization	31	2.32	2.00	1.045
Significance of AI in T&L	31	4.61	5.00	0.615
Frequency of AI Discussions	31	3.13	3.00	0.885
Students' AI Adherence	31	2.94	3.00	0.929
Faculty Impact on AI	31	4.06	4.00	1.031
Teaching & Assess. Ethics	31	4.23	4.00	0.805
Frequency of AI Communication	31	3.10	3.00	0.831
Changes in AI Adherence	31	0.58	1.00	0.502

Note: AI = Academic Integrity, T&L = Teaching and Learning.

The survey data analyzed among the 31 faculty members surveyed showed that 51.6% were aged between 31 and 40, reflecting a likely seasoned yet dynamic workforce potentially blending established pedagogical methods with innovative approaches to academic integrity.

Regarding educational attainment, the faculty's qualifications were notably high, with 58.1% holding Master's degrees and 38.7% possessing Doctoral degrees. This level of education underscores a scholarly community deeply engaged with academic rigor, which correlates with a profound understanding and commitment to upholding academic integrity.

The faculty's professional experience was distributed towards the higher end, with 41.9% displaying 10-15 years of experience and an equal percentage exceeding 15 years. This substantial experience indicates a mature teaching cohort likely to have a nuanced grasp of the complexities surrounding academic integrity.

The faculty's specializations were primarily concentrated in Business Studies (51.6%), followed by English (22.6%) and Engineering (19.4%). The diversity in disciplines suggests that the insights gained regarding academic integrity traverse various academic domains, enriching the study's findings with cross-disciplinary perspectives.

The results assessing the significance of academic honesty in teaching and learning, with 67.7% of respondents classifying it as 'Extremely significant.' This overwhelming response signals a consensus on the importance of academic integrity in educational settings, aligning with the literature that positions integrity as central to academic excellence and ethical conduct.

Conversations about academic integrity during class sessions varied, with a plurality (35.5%) acknowledging it as 'Very significant,' though nearly a third (29.0%) only considered it 'Slightly significant.' This variation highlights an area for potential development in institutional policies or faculty training, aiming to standardize the emphasis placed on these discussions to ensure they are essential in the discussion.

The perception of students' adherence to academic integrity was predominantly viewed as 'Moderate' (54.8%), indicating that while students generally follow integrity guidelines, there is notable scope for reinforcing these practices. This moderate adherence presents an opportunity for further strategic initiatives to embed integrity within the student ethos.

Faculty members felt optimistic about their role in influencing student's commitment to integrity principles, with a majority either agreeing (41.9%) or strongly agreeing (38.7%) that their emphasis on honesty impacts student behavior. This perception is a testament to educators' influential role in shaping their classrooms ethical landscape. The frequency of communication on academic integrity expectations revealed that faculty members tend to engage with their students on the matter 'Occasionally' (41.9%) to 'Frequently' (35.5%). The data suggest a commitment to regular discourse on integrity, though it also implies that making such discussions a more consistent fixture could benefit the academic community. Finally, an optimistic trend emerged, with 58.1% of the faculty observing an improvement in students adherence to academic integrity over time. This positive shift may reflect the cumulative impact of concerted efforts to cultivate a culture of integrity and the potential long-term benefits of such educational investments.

Table 2. Strategies Employed by Faculty to Promote Academic Integrity

Strategy	Percent	Percent of Cases
Syllabus Integrity Expectations (SIE)	20.9%	61.3%
Integrity Lectures (AIL)	17.6%	51.6%
Ethical Dialogue (ED)	20.9%	61.3%
Honor Pledges (HP)	16.5%	48.4%
Varied Assessment Formats (VAF)	24.2%	71.0%

Note. The total percentage exceeds 100%, as respondents could select multiple strategies. The percentage of cases indicates the percentage of respondents who chose each strategy. Strategies are based on faculty responses to the multiple-choice question regarding methods to promote academic integrity.

The survey results reveal faculty member's diverse strategies to emphasize academic integrity. Varied Assessment Formats (VAF) emerged as the most implemented strategy, with 71.0% of respondents utilizing this approach, highlighting a proactive effort to design assessments that can minimize academic dishonesty. This is followed closely by Communicating Academic Integrity Expectations in the Course Syllabus (SIE) and Encouraging Open Dialogue and Discussions about Integrity and Ethical Behavior in the Classroom (ED), adopted by 61.3% of faculty members. These strategies reflect a holistic approach that combines policy communication with active engagement to cultivate a culture of integrity.

51.6% of participants incorporated discussions on academic integrity during class lectures and discussions (AIL), suggesting that over half of the faculty prioritize integrating academic integrity topics into their instructional time. This indicates recognition of the value of integrating integrity education into regular curriculum content.

48.4% of the faculty reported using honor pledges or integrity statements before exams and assignments (HP), demonstrating a nearly even split in adopting this practice. This practice can serve as a direct reminder of ethical expectations at critical assessment moments.

Table 3. Cross-tabulation of Academic Integrity Strategies by Specialization

Specialization	Syllabus Integrity Expectations (SIE)	Academic Integrity Lectures (AIL)	Ethical Dialogue (ED)	Honor Pledges (HP)	Varied Assessment Formats (VAF)	Total
Engineering	5	3	4	3	3	6
Business Studies	8	8	11	8	12	16
Information Technology	1	2	1	1	1	2
English	5	3	3	3	6	7
Total	19	16	19	15	22	31

Note. The total number of responses exceeds the number of participants due to the multiple-response nature of the question. Percentages and totals are based on the number of respondents in each specialization category, not the total number of responses.

Within academic integrity, faculty members across various specializations have adopted various strategies to promote ethical academic practices. The deployment of Syllabus Integrity Expectations (SIE) is notably prevalent in Engineering and English, with each field reporting this strategy in half of their responses, which may indicate a strong emphasis on policy transparency in these disciplines. Academic Integrity Lectures (AIL) and Ethical Dialogue (ED) are most prominently utilized in Business Studies, reflecting a pedagogical preference for directly engaging students on integrity issues within this field. Honor Pledges (HP) are consistently employed across Engineering, Business Studies, and English, suggesting a shared appreciation for the value of commitment to ethical standards. Varied Assessment Formats (VAF) are particularly favored in Business Studies, potentially due to the dynamic nature of business education that lends itself to a multiplicity of assessment types.

Table 4 Adoption of Academic Integrity Strategies by Faculty According to Years of Experience

Years of Experience	SIE (%)	AIL (%)	ED (%)	HP (%)	VAF (%)
1-2 years	33.3	33.3	33.3	0.0	0.0
3-5 years	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0
6-9 years	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
10-15 years	53.8	53.8	76.9	46.2	61.5
More than 15 years	69.2	53.8	53.8	53.8	92.3
Total	61.3	51.6	61.3	48.4	71.0

Note. Percentages represent the proportion of faculty within each experience group who reported employing each strategy, with counts provided for context. SIE = Syllabus Integrity Expectations, AIL = Academic Integrity Lectures, ED = Ethical Dialogue, HP = Honor Pledges, VAF = Varied Assessment Formats.

The cross-tabulation between faculty years of experience and the employment of various academic integrity strategies reveals patterns that may reflect the evolution of pedagogical approaches with professional maturity. Among faculty with 1-2 years of experience, there is an equal distribution across the strategies of Syllabus Integrity Expectations (SIE), Academic Integrity Lectures (AIL), and Ethical Dialogue (ED), with each strategy being adopted by 33.3% within this group. This balanced approach suggests that newer faculty members weigh multiple methods to promote academic integrity equally.

AIL is the sole strategy reported for those with 3-5 years of experience, indicating a phase where direct instructional engagement is prioritized. However, the 6-9 years experience category data shows no reported use of these strategies. This could be attributed to the small sample size within this group.

Faculty with 10-15 years of experience demonstrate a significant increase in the use of Ethical Dialogue (76.9%), suggesting that as faculty members become more seasoned, there may be a shift toward fostering open conversations about ethics and integrity.

The most experienced faculty, with over 15 years in the field, show the highest adoption of Varied Assessment Formats (VAF) at 92.3%, which may indicate a cumulative understanding of the diverse methods required to minimize academic dishonesty. Similarly, the use of SIE and AIL remains consistently high (69.2% and 53.8%, respectively), emphasizing a sustained commitment to integrating academic integrity within policy and educational discourse.

Table 5. Frequency of Employed Teaching and Assessment Practices to Promote Academic Integrity

Teaching and Assessment Practices	Percent (%)	Percent of Cases (%)
Engaging in Class Discussions (EDD)	10.8	64.5
Consequences of Dishonesty (COD)	11.8	71.0
Plagiarism Detection (PD)	12.4	74.2
Cultivating Honesty Culture (COH)	9.1	54.8
Integrity Pledge (IP)	9.1	54.8
Open-Book Exams (OBE)	7.0	41.9
Varied Question Formats (VQF)	11.8	71.0
Timed Assessments (TA)	7.0	41.9
Individualized Assignments (IA)	9.1	54.8
Real-Life Scenarios (RLS)	11.8	71.0

Note. The percentage of cases indicates the proportion of the total number of participants who reported using each practice, with percentages exceeding 100% due to respondents' allowance for multiple selections. This table presents a consolidated view of faculty members' practices to enhance academic integrity in their courses.

The composite data from the faculty survey delineates a multifaceted approach to teaching and assessment practices that uphold academic integrity. Plagiarism Detection (PD) emerged as the most commonly reported strategy, with 74.2% of cases employing this method. This prevalence underscores the emphasis on safeguarding originality and underscores the faculty's proactive measures to detect and deter plagiarism.

Close behind, both the Consequences of Dishonesty (COD) and Real-Life Scenarios (RLS) were each employed in 71.0% of cases, indicating that faculty members are not only keen on highlighting the repercussions of academic dishonesty but also on contextualizing integrity within practical, real-world applications. This suggests a pedagogical shift towards experiential learning to instill ethical principles.

Engaging in Class Discussions (EDD), while less frequently noted in raw responses (20 instances), was reported by 64.5% of the faculty, suggesting that open dialogues about ethics are a cornerstone practice in academic settings. This finding points to the importance of interactive and reflective teaching approaches that encourage students to engage with academic integrity critically.

Varied Question Formats (VQF) align with the emphasis on plagiarism prevention, as varied assessments can mitigate the ease of dishonest practices. The data indicates a strong endorsement of this strategy, with 71.0% of cases noting its use, highlighting the faculty's commitment to diversifying assessment approaches to promote honesty.

Interestingly, 54.8% of participants reported Cultivating an Honesty Culture (COH) and requiring an Integrity Pledge (IP). These strategies reveal an inclination towards creating a foundational culture of integrity, suggesting that beyond procedural deterrents, there is an effort to embed ethical values more deeply within the student psyche.

The employment of Open-Book Exams (OBE) and Timed Assessments (TA), reported by 41.9% of cases each, may indicate a strategic use of assessment environments that inherently encourage integrity, possibly due to their structure, which can naturally limit opportunities for dishonest behavior.

Table 6. Challenges Faced by Faculty in Promoting Academic Integrity

Challenges in Academic Integrity (AI)	Percent (%)	Percent of Cases (%)
Non-Integrity Awareness (NIA)	26.5	73.3
Addressing Policy and Procedure (APP)	25.3	70.0
Preventing Dishonesty Deterrence (PDD)	25.3	70.0
Reinforcing Moral Responsibility (RMR)	22.9	63.3

Note. The percentage of Cases indicates the proportion of respondents who reported each challenge. Due to multiple selections by respondents, percentages can exceed 100%. The table reflects the multidimensional nature of faculty challenges in fostering academic integrity.

The survey data provides an enlightening perspective on faculty's challenges in fostering academic integrity among students. Non-Integrity Awareness (NIA) is the most prevalent challenge, with 73.3% of cases indicating it as a concern. This suggests a significant need for educational efforts to raise awareness about the principles of academic integrity among students. The challenges associated with Addressing Policy and Procedure (APP) and Preventing Dishonesty Deterrence (PDD) are equally represented, each identified by 70.0% of respondents. This indicates that faculty perceive establishing clear policies and actively deterring dishonest behavior as critical yet challenging components of their educational remit. The difficulty in Reinforcing Moral Responsibility (RMR) was also notable, with 63.3% of cases highlighting it. This suggests an awareness of the complexities of teaching integrity and inculcating it as a value within the student body.

Table 7. Approaches to Addressing Academic Dishonesty

Approaches	Percent (%)	Percent of Cases (%)
One-on-One Conversation (OOC)	17.9	48.4
Educational Resources (ER)	19.0	51.6
Academic Penalties (AP)	23.8	64.5
Reporting to Authorities (RTA)	20.2	54.8
Learning Opportunities (LO)	19.0	51.6

Note. The table presents the frequency and percentage of cases where faculty employed specific approaches to address instances of academic dishonesty. The percentage of Cases indicates the proportion of respondents who selected each approach, and the total can exceed 100% due to respondents selecting multiple approaches.

The survey data reveals a holistic approach faculty employs when dealing with academic dishonesty. Academic Penalties (AP) was the most common response, with 64.5% of participants identifying this as a strategy, indicating that concrete repercussions are a favored deterrent among educators. This suggests that faculty members believe in the effectiveness of disciplinary actions to enforce academic standards and discourage future misconduct.

The following approaches involve educational resources (ER) and reporting to authorities (RTA), both utilized by over half of the respondents (51.6% and 54.8%, respectively). These strategies underscore a dual commitment to punishing dishonest

behavior, educating students on the importance of academic integrity, and utilizing institutional mechanisms to uphold ethical standards.

One-on-one conversations (OOC) and providing Learning Opportunities (LO) were reported in 48.4% and 51.6% of cases, respectively. These methods reflect a more personal and developmental approach, indicating that faculty members are keen on engaging with students to understand their actions and encourage reflective learning, which could lead to a deeper internalization of integrity values.

Table 8. Faculty Responses to Handling Academic Dishonesty

Strategy for Handling Academic Dishonesty	Percent (%)	Percent of Cases (%)
Informal Warning/Dialogue (IWD)	37.9	73.3
Academic Repercussions (AR)	25.9	50.0
Additional Integrity Education (AIE)	22.4	43.3
Institutional Disciplinary Committee (IDOC)	13.8	26.7

Note. Percentage of Cases indicates the proportion of respondents who selected each strategy. The total percent of cases exceeds 100% due to respondents being able to select more than one strategy.

The table detailing faculty responses to handling academic dishonesty illustrates a preference for varied and often multi-layered approaches. Informal Warnings or Dialogue (IWD) is the most frequently employed method, with 73.3% of faculty opting for this initial, less formal step. This high rate suggests that many faculty members favor a personal and perhaps educational approach, which may allow students to reflect and self-correction without immediate escalation to formal disciplinary actions.

Half of the respondents utilize academic Repercussions (AR), such as grade deductions or assignment redo, indicating that tangible consequences are also a significant component of academic integrity policy enforcement. This strategy's substantial employment reflects an understanding that accountability measures can effectively deter dishonest behavior.

43.3% of faculty reported Additional Integrity Education (AIE), which signifies a proactive commitment to reinforcing the concept of academic integrity. This approach implies a belief in remediation and the potential for positive behavioral change through increased awareness and understanding of academic honesty principles.

The least employed strategy is referring cases to an Institutional Disciplinary Committee (IDOC), with just over a quarter of the faculty (26.7%) taking this route. This lower percentage could indicate a preference for handling incidents within the classroom or department before involving higher-level institutional governance, reserving such measures for more severe or repeated offenses.

CONCLUSION

This comprehensive study reveals an understanding of academic integrity among faculty members in higher education. It underscores the critical importance faculty places on integrity in teaching and learning, emphasizing honesty, trust, fairness, respect, and responsibility. Despite the challenges posed by digital learning environments and student pressures, educators employ diverse strategies, including syllabus integrity expectations, ethical dialogues, and varied assessment formats, to promote and maintain academic integrity. The study highlights the faculty's commitment to fostering a culture of honesty and its significant role in influencing student behavior. Adopting academic integrity strategies varies across disciplines, experience levels, and educational backgrounds, reflecting a multifaceted approach to addressing academic dishonesty. The findings suggest an evolving landscape of policy implementation, with a notable emphasis on standard enforcement and a growing recognition of the need for flexible and comprehensive policy guidelines. This study contributes valuable insights into the complexities of upholding academic integrity in modern educational settings, emphasizing the pivotal role of faculty in shaping ethical academic practices.

LIMITATION

This study acknowledges limitations that may affect our finding's generalizability and statistical power. The relatively small sample size may limit our ability to detect significant trends, particularly related to changes in plagiarism behaviors. Furthermore, the survey response rate of 64% may only partially represent part of the faculty population at all institutions.

Additionally, factors such as the diversity of students and courses taught by faculty members and potential shifts in student awareness regarding Academic Integrity over the study's duration could introduce confounding variables that may impact the internal validity of our research.

RECOMMENDATION

Challenge and Strategy Pairings:

1. Challenge - Digital Environment Promoting Academic Misconduct: There is a rise in academic misconduct due to increased access to digital resources.

Strategy - Syllabus Communication and Integrity Discussions: Communicate academic integrity expectations in the syllabus and incorporate discussions on academic integrity during class.

2. Challenge—Academic Dishonesty in Online Learning and Examinations: There are concerns about academic integrity in online classes and testing environments.

Strategy - Engagement in Ethical Dialogues and Use of Plagiarism Detection Tools: Engage students in ethical discussions and utilize plagiarism detection tools to maintain integrity.

3. Challenge - Student Pressure and Inadequate Integrity Awareness: Pressure to perform academically and need for awareness about academic integrity principles among students.

Strategy - Varied Assessment Formats and Real-World Scenarios: Employ varied assessment formats and use real-world scenarios to demonstrate the consequences of dishonest practices.

4. Challenge - Reluctance to Report Academic Misconduct: Student's hesitation to report academic misconduct by peers.

Strategy - Fostering a Classroom Culture of Honesty: Creating a classroom culture that values honesty and encourages students to report dishonest behaviors.

5. Challenge - Detecting and Addressing Plagiarism: Difficulty identifying and addressing various forms of plagiarism.

Strategy—Academic Integrity Workshops and Individual Conversations: Provide educational resources on academic integrity and conduct one-on-one conversations about consequences.

6. Challenge - Maintaining a Supportive Learning Environment While Enforcing Integrity: Striking a balance between enforcing academic integrity and maintaining a supportive learning environment.

Strategy - Implementing Academic Penalties and Integrity Education: Implement academic penalties for misconduct and provide additional integrity education opportunities.

7. Challenge—Evaluating Student Adherence to Academic Integrity: Assessing student's commitment to academic integrity through their actions and work.

Strategy—Academic Integrity Surveys and Classroom Observations: Assess the effectiveness of academic integrity initiatives using student surveys and classroom observations.

8. Challenge - Faculty Perception of Their Role in Promoting Integrity: Understanding the faculty's role and the impact of their emphasis on academic honesty.

Strategy - Faculty Development Workshops and Peer Mentoring Programs: Offering faculty development workshops on promoting academic integrity and implementing peer mentoring programs.

9. Challenge - Ethical Dilemmas of AI Usage in Academics: This challenge revolves around the ethical dilemmas posed by students who leverage AI to engage in academic dishonesty, including generating AI-driven content for assignments and assessments.

Strategy - Fostering Ethical AI Literacy and Monitoring: Address the ethical nuances of AI usage in academia through dedicated modules, promoting ethical AI literacy among students. Implement AI-powered monitoring tools to scrutinize and identify AI-generated content, ensuring the integrity of assignments and examinations. Cultivate a pedagogical environment that encourages discourse on the ethical implications of AI, fostering a culture of academic honesty and technological responsibility.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research can focus on exploring the efficacy of faculty development programs in enhancing ethical AI literacy among educators, particularly in identifying and addressing AI-driven academic dishonesty. It is crucial to investigate the impact of such programs on faculty attitudes and strategies toward academic integrity and how these changes translate into student behavior and adherence to ethical standards. Additionally, studies could examine the role of cross-disciplinary collaboration

in developing comprehensive academic integrity policies responsive to the challenges posed by digital learning environments.

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